

ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECTS ON CARBON FIBRE/EPOXY SHEAR STRENGTH

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1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre composite materials have been widely employed in the military, space and recreation industries. However, there are concerns that the mechanical properties of these materials may suffer when the material is exposed to a moist environment. Hence, the aim of this work was to examine the strength of commercial carbon fibre epoxy reinforced laminates resulting from exposure to a number of moist environments which may be encountered in practical situations.

In the assessment of environmental degradation of laminar composite materials, the interlaminar shear, flexure, and compression properties of both the matrix and the reinforcing agents are often examined. In particular, the properties of the resin and resin-fibre adhesion are considered useful properties for the determination of environmental resistance. The in-plane and interlaminar shear properties were examined to determine the influence of environment on their strength. Four and eight ply laminates of carbon fibre epoxy resin with a variety of 45 degree orientations were prepared from commercially available epoxy impregnated unidirectional carbon fibre tape using a vacuum/bag autoclaving curing process. Short term exposure to jet fuel (Jet-A1), solvent (methyl ethyl ketone MEK), and water were the media utilized for property examination. Tensile specimens were obtained from these panels and the inplane shear response of the samples were evaluated from their response to a unidirectional load to failure. A further series of specimens were prepared from unidirectional carbon tape and epoxy resin to make a laminate of fourteen plies which were utilized to determine the interlaminar shear strength by the short beam shear method (SBSM) under the same three conditions of moist environments.

2. WATER AND SOLVENT EFFECTS

One of the aspects of the effect of environment on carbon fiber epoxy composites is the deterioration of mechanical properties following the absorption of moisture when exposed to wet environments. The adverse effect on mechanical properties is a major setback to the utilization of epoxy resins. Water or solvent is absorbed into the voids of the cured epoxy resin. The sorbed water or solvent then plasticizes the resin, lowers its glass transition temperature, causes dimensional change, induces stresses and results in debonding of the fiber matrix interface as well as reducing the resin modulus and strength [1, 2].

Moisture penetration into composite materials is conducted by diffusion of water molecules into the matrix and, in some cases, the fibers [3] Additionally, moisture penetration may also occur by capillary flow along the fiber matrix interface followed by diffusion from the interface into the bulk resin and the transport by micro-cracks.

3. BASIS FOR THE 45 DEGREE SHEAR AND SHORT BEAM SHEAR TESTS

Most composite materials have low shear strengths and moduli relative to longitudinal properties. Unidirectional inplane shear stress-strain relationships are greatly influenced by the matrix and matrix/fibre interface and may be highly non-linear. Practical considerations often prevent the construction of test specimens consisting of only one layer, and so it is necessary to construct tests for multi-layer specimens and employ appropriate laminate theory to reduce the results in terms of single ply properties. In many situations the experimental determination causes some difficulty since there is no simple practical test method to induce a state of pure shear of known magnitude in a material [4]. One test method which can provide reasonable results for both the inplane shear stiffness and the shear strength is the 45 degree tensile as proposed by Petit [5].

The longitudinal (inplane) shear modulus G_{12} is given by

$$G_{12} = T_x/2(e_x - e_y) \quad \text{where } T_x \text{ is the applied tensile stress} \\ \text{and } (e_x - e_y) \text{ is the difference between the strain in the x and y directions}$$

and the inplane shear strength S_{12} is given by

$$S_{12} = P_{ult}/2A = S_{ult}/2 \quad \text{where } P_{ult} = \text{applied load at failure and} \\ S_{ult} = \text{applied stress at failure}$$

The desirable features of this test are that all experimental work is undertaken on a flat coupon of material which is representative of the actual fabrication process of a component. The desired shear stress is uniform and determined only by the applied load.

An alternate method to determine the 45 degree response to applied loads, is the interlaminar short beam shear test. The specimen is a short beam cut from a flat laminate, centre-loaded horizontally with the ends resting on two knife edge supports. The shear strength is determined from [6] as follows

$$S_{il} = 0.75P/ba \quad \text{where } S_{il} = \text{shear strength, } P = \text{the applied load,} \\ b = \text{specimen width, } a = \text{specimen thickness}$$

4. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

4.1 Materials for Laminates

Carbon tape T3T190: Prepreg density 190g/m²: resin content 35-39%
tensile strength 1.33Mpa: tensile modulus 132Mpa : tensile strain 10142 microstrain

Laminate: cured thickness per ply : 198mm (0.0078in)
per cent fibre volume: 55%

Resin System in carbon tape: Hexcel F263 resin

Resin System for Laminate: ICI Fiberite 7701 Epoxy resin

4.2 Exposure Conditions

After washing and drying the samples were conditioned in air for 21 days and dried in an oven for 24 hours at sixty degrees Celsius. The samples were placed in a non-contaminating environment before any conditioning in a liquid. Specimens were completely immersed in their environment inside three chromatography tanks under the exposure conditions given in Table 1.

Table 1. Details of Exposure Conditions

Environment	JET A-1 (jet fuel)	MEK(methyl- ethylketone)	Purified Water	Control samples-air
Temperature	23	23	71	23
Exposure (days)	1,3,5,7,14,28	1,3,5,7,14,28	1,3,5,7,14,28	
No. Samples 4-ply	6	6	6	
No. Samples 8-ply	6	6	6	

The jet fuel and MEK solutions were replaced on days 14, 16, 20 and 25 to maintain a fresh environment.

4.3 Specimen Details

Commercially available epoxy impregnated unidirectional carbon fibre tape was used as the base material. Four and eight ply laminates were prepared in the orientation of [+45/-45/-45/+45] and [+45/-45/+45/-45/-45/+45/-45/+45] respectively which resulted in symmetric laminates. Debulking took place at every ply. The samples were placed into an autoclave with controlled temperature and vacuum. The temperature in the chamber was 177C and pressure was 620 KPa until the end of the cure cycle. A two hour dwell time was allowed at temperature and pressure. The samples were cooled in the chamber.

All test specimens were obtained by cutting the laminates with a diamond saw using a water-oil coolant. Details of both the tensile and short beam shear samples are given as:

(i) The tensile specimens were manufactured according to Boeing specification for tensile specimens for unidirectional Tape (Class 1 and Class 3). One set of specimens were four ply, whilst another set were eight ply, and had the following overall physical dimensions :

Overall length 228.6 mm: Width 12.7mm:
 Tab Length 50.8mm Gauge Length 127mm

4-ply Thickness 0.71mm 8-ply Thickness 1.43mm

(ii) The Short beam Shear samples were made from the same roll of material and same resin as utilized for the tensile specimens. However, 14-ply specimens were fabricated according to ASTM D-2344 requirements for flat laminates with a span/thickness ratio of four and a length/thickness ratio of six.

Overall span 10 mm: Width 6.6mm: Depth 2.6mm

4.4 Experimental Testing

Tensile testing was performed on an Instron universal testing machine model 1185 with analytical software series IX according to ASTM D-3518. Crosshead rate was 1.3mm/min. Full scale load for the four- ply samples was 2kN and 5kN for the eight -ply samples. Five replicate tests were carried out for each type of sample from a particular environment.

Short beam shear testing was carried out according to ASTM D2344-84 at a crosshead speed of 1.3mm/min, with a full scale load of 5kN. Ten replicate tests were carried out for each type of sample from a particular environment.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tensile test results on the four and eight ply samples are shown in Figures 1 and 2 respectively. It was found that at 3000 micro strain the average shear stress and shear modulus were very similar for the four and eight ply specimens which had been exposed to jet fuel and MEK. However, the samples exposed to water showed an apparent decrease in strength throughout the exposure conditions. This may indicate that water is an important solvent for degradation of the composite strength properties.

Figure 1. Effect of environment and exposure conditions on Shear moduli of 4-ply samples.

Figure 2. Effect of environment and exposure conditions on Shear moduli of 8-ply samples.

The mechanical test results for the short beam shears samples are shown in Figure 3. The results of the test again indicate that there was little or no difference between the strength of the 4-ply and 8-ply samples immersed in MEK or jet fuel. Moreover, there was a definite decrease in the interlaminar shear strength of samples immersed in a water environment with a rapid degradation of strength occurring during the first seven days and then a slower decrease in strength.

Tanimoto [7] in his work suggested that the difference between aqueous and non aqueous environments is probably associated with the polar structure of the epoxy resin. The diffusion of

water into the epoxy may be through capillary channels or voids and occurs at a higher rate in this aqueous environments. This theory appears to be supported by the evidence from the short beam shear results with the same fiber-matrix resin system as the tensile tests.

Figure 3 Effect of environment on Short beam shear of 14-ply Composite Specimens

The results of both the tensile tests and the short beam shear tests indicate that water is a major deleterious environment for carbon fiber epoxy laminates, whereas both MEK and jet fuel had little effect on strength degradation.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Carbon fiber epoxy laminate samples were exposed to three different moist environments. Exposure to purified water has demonstrated the deleterious effect on the strength of the samples compared with both jet fuel and MEK. There appeared to be little difference in behavior between four and eight ply specimens in any of the environments.

7. REFERENCES

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FATIGUE

